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Labour/ Employment Relations of Zimbabwean Migrants in South Africa

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ABSTRACT

The economic hardships, dire poverty, political persecution among other reasons faced by Zimbabweans in recent years acted as push factors for them to migrate to South Africa in search of greener pastures. There are no pellucid statistics of the total number of illegal Zimbabweans residing in South Africa. Some of the undocumented Zimbabweans have been exposed to forced labour as well as underpayment in the labour industry due to lack of legal work documents. This research sought to examine the labour/ employment relations of Zimbabweans in South Africa. Two theories were examined and these are Stouffer's Theory of Mobility, and E. Ravenstein's laws of migration. A qualitative approach was used and the findings were drawn from the documentary analysis. The findings proved that the key challenges faced in the labour sector by Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa are fear of deportation, difficulties in securing working visas, lack of access to legal help, accommodation issues, xenophobia, marginalisation, segregation, discrimination, irregular incomes, short maternity leave, zero maternity leave benefits, non-payment of salaries, under payment of wages as well lack of work permits. In terms of policy recommendations, it was suggested that, regional cooperation on Zimbabwe Reconstruction, monitoring of the labour market, legal assistance and human rights groups, improvement in bilateral relations and diplomacy can be helpful to alleviate some of the challenges faced by Zimbabweans on South Africa.

INTRODUCTION

Migration is a phenomenon that is common and is attributed to a number of push and pull factors. A migrant is a person who moves from one country of residence to another in search of better living conditions such as employment, education among others (Requena-Méndez et al., 2021). Push factors not limited to imminent poverty, political instability, low economic activity, economic meltdown and high unemployment rates, political persecutions had a causal effect on the high levels of migration from Zimbabwe to South Africa (Ncube. Bahta & Jordaan, 2019). On the other hand pull factors such as better employment opportunities, better living standards among others led to Zimbabweans migrating to South Africa using either legal or illegal channels. The skilled ones managed to acquire work visa while some resorted to illegal entry into South Africa as cross boarder jumpers. Of great importance is the fact that countless lost their lives trying to cross the Limpopo river. The effects of an unstable and poverty stricken Zimbabwean economy! It is estimated that the number of Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa can be more than 1.5 million (Chiumia & Gibert, 2016). The number of both illegal and legal Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa has been increasing a for more than a decade. Both legal and illegal Zimbabwean migrants have contributed to the success of the South African economy. For example, a number of funeral companies have been offering repatriation services in return for a fee. On the contrary, some of the migrants have also harmed the South African economy in diverse ways such as

robbery, murder, among other social ills and evils. Despite all this, the cause of concern is on the Labour/ Employment Relations Of Zimbabwean Migrants. This research will unearth more on this. The second segment of this research will be based on the research objectives and the statement of the problem. The third section seeks to present literature review. The literature review will be divided into two segments namely theoretical and empirical literature review. The research methodology will be presented after. The focus will be on how information was collected on the subject matter. The results are going to be presented and discussed accordingly. The conclusion and the contribution of the chapter will be discussed afterwards. The last part of this research will be based on strength of the paper, weakness of the paper and reference list.

South Africa is an affiliate to the International Labour Organisation that lobbies for social and economic justice through setting international labour standards. The key unanswered question is why is South Africa neglecting sub-standard labour practises by diverse employers especially on the Zimbabwean migrants? The same migrants who are ill-treated in the employment sector contribute to the economic growth and economic development. It boggles the mind that such migrants do not have their labour rights fully protected. On the extreme end, xenophobic attacks on migrants have caused more harm than good and little has been done by the authorities to correct such anomalies. Apart from that, the effects of poor treatment of Zimbabwean migrants have been felt by the South African state at large. For

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example, a number of truck companies suffered colossal losses as their trucks were burnt during the xenophobic attacks. This impacted the business and the insurance sector as the financial costs were high. Apart from that, the delivery of goods was affected and this also posed losses to diverse stakeholders on the supply chain value on the other hand, the death of some of the truck drivers affected their families. This is so since some if not all of these drivers would send their remittances to Zimbabwe. Therefore the death of the breadwinner also exposes all the beneficiaries to the vicious jaws of poverty. The nature and effects of poor employment or labour relations of Zimbabwean migrants in South Africans is a cause for concern. If the Ubuntu philosophy does not extend to the migrants in South Africa and there is no collective effort to foster peace and tranquillity in all spheres, then the development of Africa as a region will remain a fallacy. This research seeks to explore more with a specific focus on Zimbabweans residing in South Africa. In light of the above discussions, this study aims to examine the working conditions, determine the challenges faced in the labour sector by Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa, and explore the effects of immigration on the host country.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Extended Technology Acceptance Model (ETAM)

This section seeks to present literature review. The literature review will be divided into two segments. The first segment will focus on the discussion of theories supporting the topic under study. The second segment is going to be based on the critical review of recent published work on the subject matter.

Theoretical Approach

This section seeks to present the theoretical literature review. The E. Ravenstein's laws of migration will be discussed, followed by Stouffer's Theory of Mobility.

E. Ravenstein's laws of migration

Utilizing birthplace data, Ravenstein identified a set of generalizations about inter-county migration in Britain in the 19th century that he referred to as "laws of migration." some of these generalisations are discussed below. Migration is primarily motivated by economic considerations. This is true in the case of Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa. For this first generalisation, it is authenticity is substantiated on the part of the introduction of this research as well as the empirical literature review discussion. This theory is germane to this research as it help to explain how the collapse of the Zimbabwean economy led to the exodus of Zimbabweans into South Africa in quest of greener pastures.

Another generalisation of this theory is that females are more mobile than males in their native land, but males endeavour further afield more frequently. In the Zimbabwean context, there is no pellucid statistics that shows the proportion of males and females in South Africa. However, using the basic assumption that many women in Zimbabwean are household wives, a lot of man migrated to Zimbabwe. Women were left to take care of

families. However, it cannot be denied that a significant number of both males and females Zimbabwean migrants migrated to South Africa.

Stouffer's Theory of Mobility

Stouffer developed his intervening opportunity model in 1940, claiming that there is no required relationship between mobility and distance (Stouffer, 1940:846). Instead, the observed decline in migration volume is due to an increase in the number of intervening opportunities as distance increases. According to Stouffer's model, the number of migrants from one origin to another is directly proportional to the number of opportunities at that destination and inversely proportional to the number of intervening opportunities between the origin and the destination. This theory is useful to this boom chapter but to some extent it cannot be determined if the number of opportunities in South Africa equate to the number of Zimbabwean migrants who migrated. This is so since the number of Zimbabweans migrating to South Africa continues to increase at an increasing rate.

Empirical Approach

Baison, (2021) carried out a research on the recruitment and job searching mechanisms for Zimbabwean women care workers in the domestic service sector. The study was based on qualitative research techniques and data was collected from 23 care workers in Johannesburg and Pretoria snowball sampling was used in the study. Research findings showed that the domestic workers experienced myriad challenges such as exposure to fear of deportation, labour exploitation as well as difficulties in securing working visas (Baison, 2021: 68). It was also realised that the migrant workers are afraid to approach legal authorities or the government to report such cases as they will be bound to be deported (Baison, 2021). At the end they endure the hardships and send remittances home to Zimbabwe to sustain their families.

The employment of all migrant workers in the Republic of South Africa is governed or based on the Immigration Act 13 of 2002 (amended in 2014) (RSA, 2002) (Baison, 2021). The act requires all the migrants to obtain a temporary or permanent residence permit which in many instances the low skilled workers such as maids do not meet the minimum requirements (Baison, 2021). Hence, these Zimbabwean migrant workers end up suffering from the jaws of ruthless employers who offer sub-standard working conditions. This to some extend depict that the South African labour laws are more inclined towards the support of professional workers. This problem of accessing the required permits has been affecting a lot of Zimbabweans as pointed out by (Bloch, 2008).

However, the South African government should be applauded for offering permits under diverse schemes such as the Dispensation of Zimbabweans Project, Zimbabwe Special Permit and the Zimbabwe Exemption Permit (ZEP). This helped a number of migrants to regularise their stay as well as working conditions to some extent. Although the labour laws exists that compels fair remuneration and proper working conditions, it can be

argued that bulk of the Zimbabwean migrant workers prefer to earn low wages and work under poor working conditions in South Africa than to return to Zimbabwe where their chances of getting employment are between slim and next to nothing.

Dumba & Chirisa (2010) carried out a research on the plight of illegal migrants in South Africa with a specific focus on Zimbabweans. Snowball sampling was used to obtain the respondents from the Soshanguve Area. The study was based on a qualitative approach. The target population at that time was an estimated 400 illegal Zimbabweans residing in Soshanguve.

The study concluded that the main challenges faced by illegal migrants were categorised into two. These categories are: segregation and marginalisation (Dumba & Chirisa, 2010). Apart from that, the research outcome depicted that the illegal migrants in South Africa faced segregation in terms of ; accommodation issues; and elements of deep distrust and stigmatization of the illegal migrants (Dumba & Chirisa, 2010). In terms of marginalisation, illegal Zimbabwean migrants were ultimately exposed to poverty due to factors such as joblessness, non-payment of salaries and benefits based on the illegal status of the migrants, exclusion in the labour market due to xenophobia emanating from the fact that some Zimbabweans proved to be hard workers and were preferred over other nationalities (Dumba & Chirisa, 2010: 2). Exposure to such challenges is in antagonism the key statutes of the International Labour Organisation (ILO). In particular, the International Labour Organisation Equal Remuneration Convention, 1951 (No. 100) outlines the importance of all economies in ensuring the application to all workers of the principle of equal remuneration for equal work done by men and women (International Labour Organisation, 2022).

However, in the case of illegal immigrants, that is not the case. Apart from that, Discrimination (Employment and Occupation) Convention, 1958 (No. 111) prohibits any form of discrimination in the labour market, (International Labour Organisation, 2022). The convention further requires ratifying states to declare and pursue a national policy aimed at promoting fairness and equality and treatment in relation to employment through methods appropriate to national conditions and practice, with the goal of eliminating all forms of discrimination in these areas (International Labour Organisation, 2022). Given the above position, it is pellucid that the ILO conventions are applied in partiality especially in South Africa. This is so since the South African government has its own policies and conventions that govern employment relations of migrants. The research by (Dumba & Chirisa, (2010) and Baison (2021) both showed that Zimbabweans migrants in South Africa are exposed to some form of discrimination in the labour market.

Chimonyo (2019) carried out a study on experiences of unemployed Zimbabweans, living in Johannesburg, who graduated at South African universities. From the definition posted earlier, it was clarified that migrants

can be students too. The study was based on a qualitative research technique. A total of twelve participants were selected from the target population using purposive sampling. Interviews were used for data collection.

Research findings showed that respondents confirmed that certain qualifications are less marketable and that the labor market is congested (Chimonyo, 2019: 72). Furthermore, issues such as work permits and employment quarter policies have a significant impact on foreigners in South Africa (Chimonyo, 2019:72).The above findings shows that even the skilled graduates face challenges in securing work permits. Therefore, this further point out on the nature of strictness of the South African labour laws. This is so since according to this study, it is a mammoth task to get work permit.

However, this to some extent is attributed to the fact that South Africa also wants to support its own citizens on the labour market, hence the uneasy part is then felt by Zimbabweans to secure work permits. To add more, from the study it was also realised that stigma and lack of fairness and equality in accessing resources and programmes that are meant to improve employability of Zimbabwean graduates were enormous challenges. This further shows that the South African government do cater for Zimbabwean migrants, although there are some loopholes that are detrimental to the effectiveness of the initiatives they offer. The challenges of poor working conditions, low wages, exposure of Zimbabweans migrants to unsafe working conditions has been existing for more than a decade (Bloch, 2008). This is supported by the figure below.

Figure 1.1: Average monthly pay by immigration Status
Source: Bloch (2008)

Figure 1.1 shows that the undocumented migrants earn less than the documented migrants. This shows the nature of the challenges that are faced by Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa. From this instance it is clear that the labour market in South Africa has some challenges and the environment tend to favour the migrant workers with documents. Thus, as a result, the illegal migrants are exposed to labour exploitation as they earn wages which are lower.

However, the Zimbabwean migrants keep working under such conditions even though they earn low wages. This is mainly because these migrants are using these low earnings to send remittances back home to sustain their families.

Thus, the employers in South Africa take advantage of this “cheap” labour and achieve their business interests. On the other hand, the locals who deserve market related emoluments end up unemployed. This obviously result in a high unemployment rate in South Africa as the locals keep searching for jobs that pay market-based salaries. On the other hand, the employers because they want to cut costs and maximise profit or revenue they will keep employing illegal migrants. However, the South African government has strict measures and heavy penalties for employers who employ people without enough documentation.

Machecka, Lunga, & Musarurwa, (2015) carried out a research on illegal migration by Zimbabweans into South Africa. The research was carried out qualitative research techniques. Informal interviews were used for data collection. Snowball sampling was used to obtain the respondents for the study. Research findings showed that the migrants faced a number of obstacles such as detention and deportation by law enforcement agencies in South Africa (Machecka et al., 2015: 252). Apart from that, from this research it was also discovered that a lot of Zimbabwean migrants opt for illegal channels to enter South Africa due to the bureaucratic process in acquiring the required documents (Machecka et al., 2015). As a result, these illegal migrants continue to manoeuvre the labour market without the documents as well and are then exposed to harsh working conditions.

It can therefore be deduced that once some of the Zimbabwean migrants gain access to enter South Africa, they are not motivated to seek legal documents that enable them to work. This is so because the same migrants have been exposed to bureaucratic delays to acquire documents to enter South Africa. These delays affect the migrants such that some of them do not have the patience to acquire work bias or asylums. They opt to quickly look for employment and send part of the meagre earnings back to sustain families and relatives in Zimbabwe. This depicts the concept of opportunity costs as well as costs benefit analysis. From a cost –benefit analysis point of view, it can be arguably be posited that, some of Zimbabwean migrants see it better to work earning peanuts than to wait a long time to get the work visa.

To add more , Phake (2016) carried out a research on the challenges of Zimbabweans migrants in South Africa. The study was based on qualitative research methods and data was collected through interviews. The research outcome showed that some of the Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa were exposed to discrimination and abuse when accessing some of the public and merit goods such as hospitals and schools.

Hlatshwayo (2019) carried out research on Zimbabwean migrant women in South Africa. Interviews were used for data collection in the study. Purposive sampling was used to select the respondents. Research findings showed that, pressurised workplace, stress, conflicts, xenophobia as well as negative attitude towards migrants are key obstacles that affect migrants in South Africa

(Hlatshwayo, 2019;10).

Apart from that, it was also discovered that some of the Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa suffer from irregular incomes due to the fact that they cannot secure permanent jobs in the labour market (Hlatshwayo, 2019: 10). To add more, from the study it was also discovered that some of the Zimbabwean female migrants were unfairly treated especially by being given a short maternity leave and no payment in terms of the unemployment insurance (Hlatshwayo, 2019: 12). From the same research it was also realised that some of the Zimbabwean migrants had to do on the job training, master the required skills so as to ensure that they keep the job and they earn a salary. This shows that, the South African labour market also offered an environment for skill improvement to the immigrants. This is a long-term human capital investment as even if these Zimbabwean migrants exit South Africa, they may use those skills they acquired on the job in other labour markets. Thus despite all the other negative aspects of the South African labour market condition, on this fact of human capital investment, the South African government must be applauded for awarding the Zimbabwean migrants a chance for skill development.

The South African constitution has an act that outlines the conditions of employment. This is referred to as the Basic Conditions of Employment Act (BCEA). The Basic Conditions of Employment Act 25 (1) stipulates that ‘an employee is entitled to at least four consecutive months’ maternity leave’ (Republic of South Africa 1997, 15). In reality, this law is not applied homogenously especially in the case of some of the Zimbabwean migrants who lack the legal working documents. Thus such anomalies need to be addressed since the act has a provision that states that it covers all workers in South Africa regardless of their nationality. As such, some of the employers in South Africa willingly and openly violate rights of the Zimbabwean migrant workers in the labour market. As such the harsh conditions to which the Zimbabwean migrants are exposed to are man-made. This is so because the employers choose to be above the law and the walk away Scott free.

Gumbo (2021) carried out a research on the assimilation of Zimbabwean immigrants in South Africa. The study was based on a qualitative research and documentary analysis was employed too. Research findings showed that some of the reasons for Zimbabwean migration include fear of persecution, proximity, the search for work, and food insecurity, among others (Gumbu, 2021:5863). Furthermore, from then study it was also realised certain factors that influence the assimilation process in South Africa, such as the migrant’s educational status, resources, documents, skill, and experience (Gumbu, 2021). These research findings tally with the views of Hlatshwayo (2019), Phake (2016), (Dumba & Chirisa, (2010) and Baison (2021). Both authors cited that the lack of documentation affect Zimbabwean migrants in the South African labour market.

The above literature review has shown a number of

challenges that are faced by Zimbabwean migrants in the South African labour market. Apart from that, the state of the working conditions of these migrants has been clearly described.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A research methodology refers to particular approaches,

guidelines or techniques used to define, pick, process and evaluate research knowledge. The common types of research methodologies are: qualitative, quantitative and mixed research. This study adopted a qualitative research. Research findings were drawn from the documentary analysis.

Figure 1.2: Working conditions of Zimbabwean migrants

The above figure shows that the Zimbabwean migrants are exposed to working conditions that are characterised by negative aspects such as, non-payment of salaries, low wages and abuse. Based on this research, the only positive aspect identified in as far as the working conditions issue is concerned is that the South African labour market managed to offer on the job training

Implication

Given this status quo, it is unequivocally essential for different employers to respect the various laws of the South African government as well as International Labour Organisations conventions on employment. This is critical as employers must adhere to the South African laws outlined in the constitution. The above explanation

sufficiently answers the first research question of this book chapter. The Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa have been facing a number of challenges in then labour market. The figure below is used to illustrate this.

The above figure shows that the key challenges faced in the labour sector by Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa are fear of deportation, difficulties in securing working visas, lack of access to legal help, accommodation issues, xenophobia, marginalisation, segregation, discrimination, irregular incomes, short maternity leave, zero maternity leave benefits, non -payment of salaries, under payment of wages as well lack of work permits. The table below further validates or supports some of the key challenges that have been explained prior.

Figure 1.3: Challenges faced by Zimbabwean Migrants in South Africa labour market

Source: Researcher's Construct (2022)

Table 1: Challenges faced by illegal Zimbabwean Migrants in Soshanguve

Challenge	Score	Rank	Percentage%
Unemployment	24	1	40
Unpaid labour	13	2	21.7
Accomodation	9	3	15
Xenophobic attacks	8	4	13.3
Remittance repatriation	6	5	10
N=60			100

Source: (Dumba & Chirisa, 2010)

Implication

The above challenges faced by Zimbabwean migrants implies that some of the employers in the South African labour market takes advantage that some of the migrants lack the necessary documentation that allows them to work. Thus the gaps in the labour market result in the labour exploitation of the Zimbabwean migrants. Therefore, it can be concluded that lack of work permits required in the labour market result in a lot of problems as non-payment of wages, under payment of salaries, limited maternity period among others. Although it is illegal for employers to employ people without necessary documentation, Zimbabwean illegal immigrants tend to be a cheap source of labour. Thus, although the employers cut on labour costs by employing Zimbabwean illegal immigrants they are committing crimes of contravening the Immigration Act 13 of 2002 (amended in 2014) and Basic Conditions of Employment Act. There are a number of effects that can be experienced by a host country. South Africa has been affected in a number of ways from the Zimbabwean migrants. Below are some of the benefits.

Positive effects

Below are some of the positive effects that the South African nation benefited from Zimbabwean migrants. This is presented in the form of the figure below. The

above figure shows that some of the positive effects that were experienced by South Africa are employment, increase in supply of other services (public and merit goods), infrastructure development, new business set ups, transfer of skills, increased labour supply, tax revenue as well as cultural exchanges. Instant tar which is a civil construction company focuses on the construction of tarred roads was formed by a Zimbabwean. The company has employed a number of people and as a business it pays tax to the government. Thus, the South African government gains revenue from corporate tax. Apart from that, several other businesses formed by Zimbabweans have developed the infrastructure and this is a gain to the South African economy. The presence of Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa has resulted in abundant supply of labour. Legal Zimbabwean migrants have also brought valuable skills that have led to the positive development of the economy of South Africa. In terms of the provision of public and merit goods, some of the Zimbabwean migrants have started small educational private colleges. They offer educational services and this helps the South African economy as illiteracy rates are reduced to some extent. Lastly, from a cultural perspective, there are now inter marriages between Zimbabwean and South Africans. This implies exchange of cultural values.

Figure 1.4: Positive effects of Zimbabwean Immigrants to South African economy
 Source: Researcher's Construct (2022)

Figure 1.5: Negative effects of Zimbabwean Immigrants to South African economy
 Source: Researcher's Construct (2022)

Some of the negative effects that the South African nation benefited from Zimbabwean migrants. The above figure show that some of the negative effects of Zimbabwean migrants to the South African economy are non –payment of tax, risk of cultural dilution, Stiff job competition, Murder and rape cases, and involvement

in other social ills such as cash in transit heists as well as drug abuse. Some of the Zimbabwean migrants are running business and they have been costing the South African government due to tax evasion. Apart from that, the presence of extra skilled labour force from Zimbabwe creates cut throat competition on the labour market.

This is so since the locals will be competing against the Zimbabweans. To add more, excess labour supply to some extent pushes the wages down because the employers will have a lot of alternatives to pick from. This to some extent affects the competitiveness of the South African labour market. Chief importantly to note is that this to some extent, lead to xenophobia and the common norm of “foreigners take our jobs”. As discussed under the literature review, some of the Zimbabwean migrants take any form of employment even if the wage rate is below the market based due to imminent poverty they will be suffering from.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

There is need for the Sub-Saharan Africa and the Southern African Development Community to work collaboratively to end the Zimbabwean crisis. This is so because the Zimbabwean crisis affects all the neighbouring economies. A lack of collaboration will result in more migrants leaving Zimbabwe. This obviously will result in influx of migrants and some of the adverse effects of migration to the host economies will be experienced. The various political, socio-economic problems facing Zimbabwe requires all the countries to harmoniously work together.

Monitoring of the labour market.

There is need for the strict monitoring of the labour market so as to ensure that all the aforementioned challenges are reduced. This will help to ensure that the Zimbabwean migrants are protected from every form of abuse and any form of labour exploitation. If the labour market is not monitored, the end result will be labour exploitation as well as the violation of the rights of the Zimbabwean migrants. This, the South African government can help to alleviate this challenge.

Legal assistance and Human Rights groups

It is highly recommendable that all human rights groups help to ensure that the rights of the Zimbabwean migrants are protected. Chief importantly is the need to ensure that all the migrants who require legal assistance, they get that help. This will also help to address some of the legal challenges that are faced by Zimbabwean migrants in the South African labour market.

Improvement in Bilateral Relations and Diplomacy

The South African government has done a stunning job to accommodate both legal and illegal Zimbabwean migrants in the different sectors. Some of these sectors are educational institutions labour market just to mention but a few. As such, the Zimbabwean government should further improve its bilateral relations with South Africa since the ailing economy is somehow being assisted directly and indirectly by South Africa. Since both economies have been benefiting through migration as explained earlier, string bilateral relations can help to tackle some of the challenges cited. For example, the South African government may in turn offer other lucrative benefits to migrants as it has dined in the past by offering work permits under different categories.

Poor bilateral relations can be costly especially to Zimbabwe because of all the Zimbabwean illegal mi-

grants are deported, it's an acatalectic humanitarian crisis. This is so since the Zimbabwean economy is still on its knees and more has to be done to revive the economy. Therefore, if all the illegal immigrants are deported, that will cause serious and disastrous effects to households and even other business. As such, many thanks to the South African government for its benevolence towards the Zimbabwean migrants at large.

CONCLUSION

This research sought to examine the Labour/ Employment Relations Of Zimbabwean Migrants in South. Documentary analysis was used in the study. The research findings have proved that the key challenges faced in the labour sector by Zimbabwean migrants in South Africa are fear of deportation, difficulties in securing working visas, lack of access to legal help, accommodation issues, xenophobia, marginalisation, segregation, discrimination, irregular incomes, short maternity leave, zero maternity leave benefits, non -payment of salaries, under payment of wages as well lack of work permits. some of the positive effects that were experienced by South Africa are employment, increase in supply of other services (public and merit goods), infrastructure development, new business set ups, transfer of skills, increased labour supply, tax revenue as well as cultural exchanges. Apart from that, some of the negative effects of Zimbabwean migrants to the South African economy are non -payment of tax, risk of cultural dilution, Stiff job competition, Murder and rape cases, and involvement in other social ills such as cash in transit heists as well as drug abuse.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study will expand knowledge and information available on immigrants in the Sub-Saharan Africa region. The study will also assist in the monitoring and implementation of section 23 of the South African Constitution (Act 200 of 1993) which emphasize on fair labour practices for all, be it legal or illegal employees. Findings may inform the formulation of improved migration policies that regulate the movement of people across borders. It will also contribute to the UN Sustainable Development Goal 10 which aims to reduce inequality within and among countries, specifically target 10.7 which is developed to facilitate orderly, safe, regular and responsible migration and mobility of people, through the implementation of planned and well managed migration policies.

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